

Kinetics of the Metal Ion Oxidation of Phenyl Phosphonous acid in Solution : Part III Oxidation by Manganese (III)

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Kinetics of the oxidation of phenyl phosphonous acid by manganese (III) in sulphuric acid has been studied. The reaction has been found to be of first order with respect to both phenyl phosphonous acid and manganese (III). Hydrogen ions retard the rate of reaction. The addition of sodium sulphate and increase in dielectric constant enhance the rate of reaction. A suitable mechanism for the oxidation process has been proposed.

THE kinetics of several oxidation-reduction reactions involving manganese (III) have been studied¹. The mechanism of the oxidation of numerous organic compounds by manganese (III) pyrophosphate has also been suggested by Waters and his coworkers². The oxidation of phenyl phosphonous acid by both vanadium (V)³ and chromium (VI)⁴ has been studied earlier by Sen Gupta et. al It was, therefore, intended to carry out further oxidation studies using a typical one electron transfer oxidant such as manganese (III). The results of such studies have been incorporated in this report.

Reagents : All the chemicals used were of BDH (AnalaR) or equivalent grades. The method of preparation of phenyl phosphonous acid has been described elsewhere³. Manganese (III) sulphate was prepared by the method which is based on the oxidation of manganese (II) sulphate with potassium permanganate⁵. The solution after preparation was stored in blue bottles and placed in a refrigerator when not in use. The solution was standardised before use by titrating it against standard ferrous ammonium sulphate. All solutions were prepared with freshly prepared double distilled water.

Experimental

The absorption spectra of manganese (III) solution was measured with a Beckman DB model spectrophotometer using a cell of path length 0.1 cm. The kinetics of the reactions of phenyl phosphonous acid by manganese (III) in sulphuric acid were followed in a Beckman DU model spectrophotometer using a cell of 1 cm path length at 500 nm at which manganese (III) shows maximum absorbance. The experimental set up has been described elsewhere⁴. The pseudo first order rate constants have been calculated from the slopes of the lines obtained by plotting $\log [\text{Mn(III)}]$ against time. The error in the analyses of rate constants was always between 1-5% depending upon the temperature of experiment. In most experiments satisfactory results were obtained which were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. We have observed that decomposition of manganese(III) is not more than 5% per hour even at higher tempera-

tures and blank experiments were performed where decomposition was appreciable. The rate of decrease of manganese (III) was followed upto 60% conversion of initial manganese (III).

Results

Absorption spectra of reactants and products : The absorption spectra of manganese (III) solutions was noted both in the ultraviolet and in the visible regions ranging from 200-700 nm. The manganese (III) solution of strength $6.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ ($\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 5.5 M$) has got no absorption maximum in the ultraviolet region. A broad band, on the other hand, in the visible region at around 500 nm has been observed at higher manganese (III)

Fig. 1 : Absorption spectra of manganese (III) solution in 5.5 M H_2SO_4 in the ultraviolet and visible regions.
1, $[\text{Mn(III)}] = 3.0 \times 10^{-2} M$; 2, $[\text{Mn(III)}] = 2.4 \times 10^{-2} M$;
3, $[\text{Mn(III)}] = 1.8 \times 10^{-2} M$; 4, $[\text{Mn(III)}] = 6.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.
1-3, visible region ; 4, ultraviolet region.

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concentrations, thus supporting the observation of previous workers⁶ who showed that aquomanganic compound has one broad band at around $20,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Manganese (II) is nearly transparent at this wavelength. The absorption spectra of different concentrations of manganese (III) solution e.g. 1.8×10^{-2} , 2.4×10^{-2} and $3.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ ($H_2SO_4 = 5.5 M$) were recorded with an idea to see whether there is any spectral shift with changes in the concentration of manganese(III) solution. The spectral pattern as well as maxima do not change with changes in the concentration of manganese (III) (Fig. 1). Moreover, Beer's law has been found to be valid for the compound in the range $(1.0-5.0) \times 10^{-3} M$ indicating that the compound is stable in this concentration range. This is in agreement with the observation made earlier by Selim and Lingane⁷ that in the region of $5-7.0 M$ sulphuric acid, manganese (III) is quite stable with respect to both reduction by water and to precipitation of oxide. Again, neither phenyl phosphonous nor phenyl phosphonic acid has got any absorption in the visible region.

Stoichiometry : Phenyl phosphonous acid when mixed with large excess of manganese(III), acidified with sulphuric acid and kept for 24 hr consumed 2.05 equivalents of oxidant per mole of the substrate.

Test for free radical : The addition of acrylamide to the reaction mixture during the oxidation by manganese (III) increased the viscosity of the same enormously indicating the formation of free radical in solution.

Effect of reactant concentrations : To determine order with respect to manganese (III), the reactions were initially carried out at different concentrations of oxidant. For this, the concentrations of phenyl phosphonous acid and hydrogen ion were kept fixed in each experiment but the concentrations of manganese (III) were varied only between the limits $(4.5-6.0) \times 10^{-3} M$. The order with respect to manganese (III) is one since first order rate constant is found to be independent of initial manganese (III) (Table 1). Again, some experiments were also performed with various concentrations of reducing substrate, when $[substrate] \gg [oxidant]$. The concentrations of manganese (III) and hydrogen ions were always $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $6.0 M$ respectively for each run. The values of k_1 at different substrate concentrations have been recorded in Table 2. The plot of reciprocal of pseudo first order rate constant against reciprocal of substrate concentration is linear passing through the origin suggesting that the order with respect to substrate is unity (Fig. 2). This further suggests that an intermediate complex formation between substrate and oxidant is unlikely.

Fig. 2: Plots of reciprocal of pseudo first order rate constant against reciprocal of substrate concentrations at 30, 35, 40 and 45°.

$$[Mn(III)] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} M, [H^+] = 6.0 M.$$

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF OXIDANT ON THE PSEUDO FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT

[PhPO₂H₂]=2.84 × 10⁻² M, [H₂SO₄⁺]=7.2 M, Temp. = 35°

[Mn(III)] × 10 ³ M	4.0	5.0	5.5	6.0
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ (sec ⁻¹)	1.63	1.56	1.58	1.63

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SUBSTRATE CONCENTRATION ON THE REACTION

[Mn(III)]=4.0 × 10⁻³ M, [H₂SO₄⁺]=6.0 M

[PhPO ₂ H ₂] × 10 ² M	30°	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ (sec ⁻¹)		45°
1.706	0.576	1.15	1.61	2.99
2.275	0.852	1.49	2.41	3.91
2.844	1.01	1.81	—	4.63
3.413	—	2.14	3.18	5.59
3.981	1.29	—	3.57	—

Effect of acids on the reaction: The acidity of reaction mixture was varied by the addition of sulphuric acid. Each reaction was carried out at constant [manganese (III)], and [PhPO₂H₂]₀ but ionic strength could not be maintained constant. The pseudo first order rate constants decreases with increase in acid concentrations. The products k₁ [H₂SO₄] have been recorded in Table 3 which indicate that the rate is inversely proportional to sulphuric acid concentrations.

TABLE 3—INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT ACIDS ON THE REACTION RATE

A) [PhPO₂H₂]=1.706 × 10⁻² M, [Mn(III)]=4.0 × 10⁻³ M, Temp=25°
 B) [PhPO₂H₂]=1.706 × 10⁻² M, [Mn(III)]=4.0 × 10⁻³ M, Temp = 35°

[H ₂ SO ₄] in M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ (sec ⁻¹)	k ₁ [H ₂ SO ₄] × 10 ⁴	%CH ₃ COOH (v/v)	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ (sec ⁻¹)
5.0	0.525	2.62	0	1.15
6.0	0.484	2.90	10	1.08
6.6	0.437	2.88	25	1.04
7.8	0.391	3.05	30	0.990
8.0	0.380	3.04	40	0.962

The reaction was studied in different acetic acid-water (v/v) mixtures. The rate of reaction has a tendency to decrease with the increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the reaction mixture though the decrease is not significant. This is in contrast to the observation made earlier⁹ in connection with the oxidation of phenyl phosphonous acid by vanadium (V) where increase in rate with increase in acetic acid was observed. The data, however, could not be correlated with previous observations, although the present result indicates that the reaction takes place between ion and neutral molecule.

Effect of foreign salts on the reaction rate: The effect of addition of salts on the pseudo first order rate for manganese (III) oxidation has been studied (Table 4). Sodium sulphate increases the rate of reaction. This indicates that one of the reactive species is a positive one since according to Amis⁸, the reaction which increases with the increase in salt concentration is a positive ion-dipole reaction. Manganese (II) is known to affect the rate of oxidation of some organic

TABLE 4—INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT SALTS ON THE REACTION RATE

[PhPO₂H₂]=1.706 × 10⁻² M, [Mn(III)]=4.0 × 10⁻³ M, [H₂SO₄⁺]=6.0 M, Temp = 35°

[Na ₂ SO ₄] × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ (sec ⁻¹)	[MnSO ₄] × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ (sec ⁻¹)
0	1.15	0	1.15
1.05	1.38	2.5	1.22
1.40	1.54	5.0	1.20
1.75	1.65	10.0	1.21
2.10	1.79	—	—

compounds^{9,10} where the active oxidant is manganese (IV) and this has been attributed to its effect on the equilibrium (1). Absence of any effect of manganese (II) on the rate of oxidation suggests that manganese (III) is the only oxidising species.

Influence of temperature on the specific reaction rate: The second order rate constants H₂SO₄=6.0 M at different substrate concentrations

were calculated from the relation, $k_2 = \frac{k_1}{[\text{PhPO}_2\text{H}_2]}$.

The average of four runs have been calculated to be 3.48 × 10⁻³, 6.50 × 10⁻³, 9.28 × 10⁻³ and 16.86 × 10⁻³ (lit. mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹) at 30, 35, 40, 45° respectively. The energy of activation has been calculated to be 19.8 ± 1.0 kcal mole from the slope of the conventional log k₂ vs. $\frac{1}{T}$ plot. The other activation parameters e. g.

log PZ, -ΔS[‡] and ΔG[‡] have been calculated to be 11.83 ± 0.1 (lit. mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹), 4.48 ± 0.2 (e.u.) and 21.2 ± 0.06 kcal (at 313°K) respectively. The frequency factor as well as entropy change are high enough to suggest that the reaction is a bimolecular one¹¹. The analyses thermodynamic data (Table 5) show that the reactions by different transition metal ions are as a whole characterized by wide range of activation parameters although ΔG[‡] values do not differ appreciably. The ΔG[‡] values are almost of the same order possibly because Δ[‡] and ΔS[‡] compensate each other. The activation parameters are not widely different for other redox reactions in perchloric acid although they are highly different in sulphuric acid. It is already known that both vanadium (V) and manganese (III) cations are complexed by sulphate groups¹ and do not form any complexes with perchlorate ion. Consequently higher activation parameters are to be expected in sulphuric acid.

Discussion

The dependence of acid on reaction rate suggests that MnHSO₄²⁺ is the reacting species in solution since with the increase in acid concentration, the concentration of MnHSO₄²⁺ would decrease according to the following equilibrium.

TABLE 5—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF DIFFERENT REDOX REACTIONS

Oxidant	Medium	ΔH^\ddagger (kcal/mole)	ΔS^\ddagger (e.u.)	ΔG^\ddagger (kcal/mole)
Vanadium (V) ¹	HClO ₄	12.2 ± 0.4	- 36.6 ± 1.3	23.8 ± 0.8
Vanadium (V) ²	H ₂ SO ₄	28.8 ± 0.5	+ 15.3 ± 1.5	23.7 ± 1.0
Chromium (VI) ₂	HClO ₄	10.3 ± 1.2	- 40.2 ± 3.9	22.7 ± 2.4
Manganese (III)	H ₂ SO ₄	19.8 ± 1.0	- 4.48 ± 0.2	21.2 ± 0.6

Since dissociation constant of phenyl phosphonous acid is of the order of 10^{-3} , it would remain as an undissociated form in the presence of high mineral acid concentration. Consequently, the reaction takes place by the interaction of MnHSO_4^{2+} with active form of undissociated phenyl phosphonous acid, (since active form predominates in the acid medium) to give a free radical PhPO_2H and MnHSO_4^+ in the rate determining step. The free radical would further react with oxidant to give phosphonium ion and MnHSO_4^+ . The phosphonium ion finally gives the stable product phenyl phosphonic acid by reacting rapidly with water.

The steps of the reaction are,

The formation of intermediate compound, on the other hand, between PhPO_2H_2 and manganese (III) cannot be totally ruled out although kinetic evidence is insignificant and phenyl phosphonic acid may be generated in the rate determining step by the breakdown of the $[\text{Mn}(\text{III})-\text{PhPO}_2\text{H}]^{2+}$ complex in the solvolysis step (7). The reaction may, therefore, proceed according to the following steps,

The effect of solvent composition on the rate support the above solvolysis step since with the increase in water content, the rate of reaction is increased (Table 3). Manganese (I) which is formed in step (7) reacts further with manganese (III) to give two molecules of manganese (II) according to step (8). Though uncommon, the existence of univalent manganese compound is also known in the literature^{1,2}. Moreover, the redox potential of manganese (I)→manganese (II) couple is too low and even lower than that of vanadium (III)→vanadium (IV) couple which is -0.36 volt. Consequently, the formation of manganese (II) by the interaction of manganese (I) and manganese (III) by fast step (8) cannot be totally ruled out.

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